

5 – 8 June 2024, University of Bern, Switzerland

Climate of the past and societal responses to environmental changes

The conference is organized by researchers from history, archaeology, environmental and climate sciences of the Universities of Bern and Yale. It aims to provide a comprehensive framework, exploring the broader theme of societal responses to historical climate changes and the evolution of societies, institutions, and economies in both prehistoric and historical contexts. Key topics are:

- Climate and environmental changes in the societal context
- Social vulnerability, and resilience to climatic change
- Spatial and temporal scales
- Novel methods and approaches, including computational methods, to better understand human-environmental systems

Organizing Committee

Prof. Dr. Joseph Manning, Yale University, New Haven, USA
Prof. Dr. Albert Hafner, University of Bern, Switzerland
Prof. Dr. Martin Grosjean, University of Bern, Switzerland
Dr. Caroline Heitz, University of Bern, Switzerland

Dr. Martin Hinz, University of Bern, Switzerland
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Time	Session 1. Pleistocene to Holocene Environmental Transformations. Chair: Joseph Manning
08.30 – 08.40	Welcome and information
08.40 – 09.00	<p>From glacial to Green Sahara to the post-industrial world: fire interactions with climate, vegetation, and human land use change in African ecosystems</p> <p>Nicholas A. O'Mara*^{1,2}, Esther N. Githumbi³, Ali Aldous¹, Juliette Garcia¹, Marie Norwood⁴, A. Carla Staver^{2,4}, Jennifer R. Marlon^{1,2}</p> <p>¹Yale School of the Environment, Yale University, USA; ²Yale Institute for Biospheric Studies, Yale University, USA; ³Institute of Soil Science and Site Ecology, TUD Dresden University of Technology, Germany; ⁴Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, Yale University, USA; nicholas.omara@yale.edu</p>
09.00 – 09.20	<p>A «Multiple Evidence Base Approach» to the compound impact of climate change and the ~13ka BP Laacher See volcanic eruption on Final Palaeolithic foragers in Europe</p> <p>Felix Riede*</p> <p>Aarhus University, Denmark; f.riede@cas.au.dk</p>
09.20 – 09.40	<p>Cultural discontinuity and cultural response to rapid climate changes at the end of the Pleistocene in the Middle Dnieper basin</p> <p>Pavlo Shydlovskiy¹, Marharyta Chymyrys¹, Ostap Tsvirkun²</p> <p>¹Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine; ²National Museum of the History of Ukraine; pav.shy@gmail.com</p>
09.40 – 10.00	<p>Assessing the climate resilience of human populations during prehistory</p> <p>Ariane Burke^{1,2}, Simon Paquin¹, Benjamin Albouy¹, Timothee Poisot¹, Masa Kageyama³</p> <p>¹Universite de Montreal, Canada; ²University of Bern, Oeschger Centre for Climate Change Research (OCCR); ³Laboratoire des Sciences du Climat et de l'Environnement, LSCE (UMR 8212); a.burke@umontreal.ca</p>
10.00 – 10.20	<p>Late Quaternary Climate Change and the Peopling of the Arid and Semiarid Regions of Chile</p> <p>Claudio Latorre Hidalgo*^{1,2}, Mauricio Lima^{1,3}, Eugenia M. Gayo^{3,4}, Carolina Godoy-Aguirre¹, Calogero M. Santoro⁵</p> <p>¹Facultad de Ciencias Biológicas, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; ²Institute of Ecology and Biodiversity (IEB), Chile; ³Center for Applied Ecology (CAPES), Chile; ⁴Facultad de Arquitectura y Urbanismo, Universidad de Chile; ⁵Instituto de Alta Investigación, Universidad de Tarapacá, Chile; clatorreh@uc.cl</p>
10.20 – 11.00	COFFEE BREAK
Time	Session 2. Bronze Age to Ancient Nile Valley. Chair: Martin Hinz
11.00 – 11.20	<p>Same but different? A comparative analysis of societal and climate changes in Bronze Age Greece</p> <p>Erika Weiberg*¹, Martin Finné^{1,2}</p> <p>¹Department of Archaeology and Ancient History, Uppsala University, Sweden; ²Department of Human Geography, Uppsala University, Sweden; erika.weiberg@antiken.uu.se</p>
11.20 – 11.40	<p>Volcanic Forcing of the East African Monsoon and Egyptian History</p> <p>Joe Manning¹, Francis Ludlow²</p> <p>¹Yale University, United States of America; ²Trinity College Dublin; joseph.manning@yale.edu</p>
11.40 – 12.00	<p>Simulating Inundated Area for Ptolemaic Nile River Flooding</p> <p>James H. Stagge¹, Irene F. Munyejuru¹, Joseph Morgan², Francis M. Ludlow³, Joseph G. Manning⁴</p> <p>¹The Ohio State University, Department of Civil, Environmental and Geodetic Engineering; ²Florida State University, Department of Classics; ³Trinity College Dublin, Department of History; ⁴Yale University, Department of History; stagge.11@osu.edu</p>
12.00 – 12.20	<p>A Bioarchaeological Perspective on Human Responses to Climate Change in the Ancient Nile Valley</p> <p>Michele R. Buzon*¹, Iwona Koziaradzka-Ogunmakin²</p> <p>¹Purdue University, USA; ²PCMA University of Warsaw and University of Exeter; mbuzon@purdue.edu</p>
12.20 – 14.00	LUNCH BREAK

Session 1. Pleistocene to Holocene Environmental Transformations. Chair: Joseph Manning

09.20 – 09.40 | Friday, June 07, 2024

Cultural discontinuity and cultural response to rapid climate changes at the end of the Pleistocene in the Middle Dnieper basin
Pavlo Shydlovskyi¹, Marharyta Chymyrys¹, Ostap Tsvirkun²

¹Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine; ²National Museum of the History of Ukraine; pav.shy@gmail.com

The traditional view of cultural development in the Stone Age often based on the idea of gradual replacement, where one cultural phenomenon is superseded by another, supposedly more developed one. This perspective fosters the notion of cultural stability, portraying a continuous growth in human achievements, expansion of the resource base, and successful use of natural resources by prehistoric groups. However, presenting such linear schemes can create misconceptions regarding the accuracy and internal logic of historical development, fostering a false sense of stability and infinite growth potential. Recent research in the field of prehistoric archaeology in Eastern Europe, coupled with the rapid advancements in natural sciences and radiocarbon dating, is fundamentally reshaping our understanding of the development of prehistoric cultures. Contrary to the previously held belief in a slow, steady, and gradual progression, modern studies of the Upper Palaeolithic of the Middle Dnieper region allow us to reconstruct a nuanced picture of the interaction between nature and society spanning from the appearance of anatomically modern humans to the end of the Pleistocene.

A pivotal period in human existence in northern Ukraine was the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM), which marks a chronological gap of several millennia in the distribution of archaeological sites (23–19 ka calBP). This temporal discontinuity raises questions about the evolutionary relationship between the late Gravettian industries and the Middle Dnieper Epigravettian.

Within the eastern Epigravettian in the end of the Pleistocene, several synchronous types of industries can be distinguished: the Mezhyrichian, Mizynian, and Yudinovian. These cultures shared common features, such as the tradition of constructing settlements with mammoth-bone dwellings, the extensive use of mammoth remains in daily life for fuel, building materials, and tool manufacturing, as well as the widespread use of stylized figurines crafted from tusk. The time of the spread of these industries coincides with the relative mitigation of the climate following the LGM and preceding the onset of the last Würm interstadial (19–14 ka calBP). During this period, several levels of landscape mastery can be observed, characterized by complex site structures, a certain settlement system, and the development of patterns of seasonal mobility. Architectural elements and household objects found in these sites, as well as the settlements themselves, exhibit rhythmicity and symmetry, indicative of the organization of living space by prehistoric hunters.

Following the peak of the Epigravettian mammoth hunters' culture, during the transition to the final Pleistocene, it is possible to observe the absence of technological successors to the Epigravettian industry in these regions in the subsequent millennia (13–11 ka calBP). Archaeological data suggest that vast areas were uninhabited, and new traditions associated with North European industries of making arrowheads on blades appeared during the Younger Dryas. Current data allow us to assert that global changes have led to depopulation in large areas, the disappearance of large groups of people during times of crisis, and complex migration processes. This knowledge enables us to draw conclusions about the vulnerability of human networks to abrupt climate change and underscores the necessity of objectively analyzing the current situation.